

Seroprevalence of *Mycobacterium bovis* In Camel Slaughtered at Sokoto Metropolitan Abattoir, Sokoto Nigeria

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Seroprevalence of *Mycobacterium bovis* antibodies in camel was determined at Sokoto Metropolitan abattoir, Sokoto State, Nigeria using immunochromatographic assay technique. Two hundred and fifty (250) blood samples comprising 188 males (75.2%) and 62 females (24.8%) were collected and screened against *M. bovis* antibodies. In this abattoir-based study the Seroprevalence of tuberculosis in camels was found to be 30.8%. Seventy-seven positive samples were detected, with the males having 50 positive samples representing (26.6%) and the females having 27 positive samples representing (43.5%) of the population of the sampled animals respectively. The results also indicate significant statistical association between the seroprevalence of camel tuberculosis and sex, while no statistical association occur between the age and seroprevalence of camel tuberculosis.

Keywords; Abattoir, Camel, *Mycobacterium bovis*, Nigeria, Seroprevalence, Sokoto State

INTRODUCTION

Camel is an ancient animal well known in the history of human civilization. It belongs to the class mammalia, the order Artiodactyla; sub-order Tylopoda, and family Camelidae (Al Haj and Al Kanhal, 2010). It has been domesticated for transportation, meat, clothing and milk over 400 years ago (Wilson, 1984). The meat is of good quality especially in areas where other meat animals find it difficult to thrive (Kadim *et al.*, 2008) and the milk quality is of comparable quality to cattle and it provides milk for longer duration compared to other similarly domesticated animals (Mehaia *et al.*, 1995). There are two known species of camels, namely; *Camelus*

bacterianus (the two humped camel) and *Camelus dromedarius* (the one humped camel) which is also called the trade camel or Arabian camel (Dorman, 1986).

Tuberculosis is a common and, in many cases, lethal, infectious disease caused by various strains of *Mycobacteria* (Kumar *et al.*, 2007). It is characterized by the formation of granulomas in tissues and organs more significantly in the lungs, lymph nodes intestines, liver, kidneys (Shitaye *et* goats, horses, dogs, cats, badgers, lions, elephants, dears, primates and man (Ayele *et al.*, 2007). Bovine tuberculosis is an important disease of both economic and public health importance (Sudre *et al.*, 1992). Though, primarily a bovine problem but infects and causes tuberculosis in camels, pigs, *al.*, 2004). In Camels tuberculosis (Tb) is a chronic, contagious, granulomatous disease caused by *Mycobacteria species*

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belonging to the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTC) (Thoen *et al.*, 2006). The disease affects many vertebrate animals and manifests particularly in lungs and lymph nodes but also in other organs. Camelids were not considered highly susceptible to Tb (Fowler, 2010), but in recent years serious concern has arisen about Tb in New World Camelids (NWCs), particularly llamas and Alpacas, in some countries where they are reared (and not just countries in their native South America). For example, Tb is a serious emerging disease in the steadily increasing NWC population of the United Kingdom (UK) (Twomey *et al.*, 2008). Tuberculosis also affects Old World Camelids (OWCs), including Dromedaries and Bactrian camels (Mustafa, 1987). *M. microti* have been isolated from camelids (Barlow *et al.*, 1999). Atypical (non-MTC) Mycobacteria have also been isolated from camelids; for example, *M. kansasii* has been associated with clinical signs and pathological lesions similar to those of classic Tb (Johnson *et al.*, 1993). In most cases of Tb in camelids, tubercles are characterized histologically by granuloma formation, with infiltration by epithelioid macrophages, lymphocytes, plasma cells and neutrophils, central caseous necrosis and variable calcification and fibroblastic reaction (Bush *et al.*, 1990). Giant cells have rarely been described, except by (Zanolari *et al.*, 2009), who found them in eight of 11 *M. microti* - infected NWCs. Bovine tuberculosis is a chronic contagious respiratory disease of cattle spreading horizontally within and between species, by aerosol and ingestion. Bovine tuberculosis is occurring in almost all developed and developing nations of the world. The incidence of the disease not only higher in the developing nations but in the absence of any national control and eradication program is also increasing worldwide particularly in Asian, African and Latin American countries.

Tuberculosis is still the greatest single cause of human morbidity and mortality, in many developing countries (Kovalev, 1980). *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* is the most frequent cause of human tuberculosis (HTb), but some cases are caused by *M. bovis* (Meissener and Schroder, 1974). Bovine tuberculosis used to be a serious zoonosis and represented a tremendous public health problem in developed countries, mainly through the consumption of unpasteurized milk (Collins and Grange, 1987). However, the disease was controlled in cattle through designated test and slaughter schemes together with milk pasteurization and public education, these countries drastically reduced and, in some cases, control the transmission of BTb to humans (Danker *et al.*, 1993).

In developing countries especially in Africa, where *M. bovis* infection has been reported in a wide range of animal species, is still prevalent and is responsible for significant economic loss in animal production, through reduced milk yields, abattoir carcass condemnation, low meat yield through emaciation and low reproductive

performance. BTb has also been implicated in the increase of human health problem (Cosivi *et al.*, 1998). Bovine tuberculosis is known to be a major cause of human extra pulmonary tuberculosis specifically the gastrointestinal tuberculosis, and is of particular concern in developing countries where bovine milk is not often pasteurized (Sonnenberg *et al.*, 2001). The reason for this is that the major mode of exposure to *M. bovis* infection in human mainly manifest as an extra pulmonary form, particularly causing cervical lymphadenitis.

In Nigeria the human cases associated with *M. bovis* infection both pulmonary and extra pulmonary have been described from the limited survey research which have been reported over the last 30 years in the country, prevalence of bovine tuberculosis due to *M. bovis* ranges from 2.5% in 1976 to 14% in 2007 (Idigbe *et al.*, 1986). About 30 camels are slaughtered daily in Sokoto Metropolitan abattoir, yet there is dearth of information about camel tuberculosis in the study area. Tuberculosis is one of the major global reportable zoonotic diseases, killing approximately 1.5 to 2 million people every year (Thoen *et al.*, 2009). Camel milk is a potential source of infection, as *M. bovis* was isolated from pooled milk samples from camels (Abdurahman and Bornstein, 1991).

The aim of the present study is to determine the prevalence of *Mycobacterium bovis* antibodies in camels slaughtered at Sokoto Metropolitan abattoir. To determine the association of *M. bovis* antibodies in relation to age and sex of slaughtered camels. Determine the presence of postmortem lesions in serum sampled animals. The justification of the studies is the study will provide information on the prevalence of camel tuberculosis due to *M. bovis* in the study area., The study will also introduce the use of rapid screening test for camel tuberculosis in the abattoir, Information generated can serve as bases for further research on camel tuberculosis in the State and Nigeria in general.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The work was conducted at Sokoto Metropolitan abattoir, located in the capital city of Sokoto state. Sokoto is located in the extreme North West of Nigeria, near to the confluence of Sokoto River and the Rima River. As at 2005 it has an estimated population of more than 4.2 million. Sokoto is a dry Sahel, surrounded by sandy savannah and dry hills. With an annual average temperature of 28.3°C (82.9°F), which makes it, on the whole, very hot area (<http://www.onlinenigeria.com> accessed 2013). It has a land area of approximately 56000 square kilometers, and is located between longitude 5° 14" east and latitude 13° 04" North (Anon,

Table 1: Age Estimation in Camels

Age	Features
1 month + 1 year	Eruption of all deciduate teeth D11, D12, D13. D11 in wear.
About 2 years	D12 in wear.
About 3 years	All the incisors are quite worn down with square or irregular table and eruption of permanent canine.
About 4 years	Eruption of permanent 11 (central). Eruption of permanent 12 (lateral).
About 5 years	Eruption of permanent 13 (corner).
About 6 years	All the permanent incisors have erupted and canine teeth have reached it full size.
About 7 years	Permanent 11 in wear.
About 7½ years	Permanent 12 and 13 in wear. Canine stump or blunt. 11 are stub with square table.
About 9 years	12 are stub with square table.
About 10 years	13 are stub with square table.
About 11 years	Increase wide gap in interdental space.
About 12 years	
About 13 years	
About 14 years	
About 15 years	

2001). The metropolis is mainly made up of Sokoto North and Sokoto South Local Government areas. The state is bordered to the North by Niger Republic, to the East by Zamfara State and to the South and West by Kebbi State (Anon, 2001). The State ranked second in livestock population in Nigeria (N.P.C., 2006). The occupation of the inhabitants includes rearing of animals and farming. The region lifeline for growing crops is the floodplains of the Sokoto – Rima River system.

Sampling

Convenience sampling method was employed. Camels brought for slaughter in the abattoir were used for the study, for a period of 6 weeks with no intervals. About 250 camels were slaughtered within the period, and were used for the work.

Determination of the Sample Size

The sample size was determined using the formula:

$$n = \{z^2 P (1-P)\}/d^2 \text{ (Thrusfield, 2002).}$$

Where n is sample size, Z is level of confidence (1.96 SE at 95%), prevalence of 17% (Kudi *et al.*, 2012) was used in the sample size determination and desired precision of 5%.

$$n = \{1.96^2 \times 0.17 \times (1-0.17)\}/0.005^2$$

$$n = 3.8416 \times 0.17 \times 0.83/0.0025$$

$$n = 0.54204976/0.0025$$

$$n = 216.8$$

$$n = 217$$

Therefore, minimum samples of 217 were to be collected. But, 250 samples were collected for the purpose of this research.

Sample Collection

2mls of blood sample were collected in a sterile centrifugal tube from camel at point of slaughter in the abattoir. The centrifugal tubes were immediately capped and labeled (serial number and date) using indelible maker. The collected sample was then transported in an ice packed container to the Public Health and Preventive Medicine laboratory at Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, where they were allowed to clot and centrifuged to collect serum. The serum samples were immediately analyzed.

Ageing of Camels

Age estimation using rostral dentition in camel is possible but required some experience and skills. This is mainly because it is sometimes difficult to distinguish clearly between deciduate and permanent incisors as there was no marked difference in size of the two stages as there is in true ruminant (Ferguson, 1990). The only way to age an animal accurately is to know the date of birth but where these records are not available, various anatomical features are used to estimate age (delahunta, 1986). The most convenient teeth for ageing are the incisors (front teeth), the canines and the first premolars. The remaining teeth are hidden by the cheeks. Camel has a narrow mouth and if the teeth within the cheeks need to be properly examined, an oral speculum or

mouth gap and a light source may be required, good restraint is always necessary.

Following full tooth development, wear commences. The rate of wear is influenced by the camel particular environment, which can influence the amount of abrasive material contacted during eating. The incisors of camel teeth are the teeth that cut across the front of the mouth. They have six (2 centrals, 2 laterals and 2 corners) in the lower jaw, and only two corners in the upper jaw that tend to be conical in shape. These upper incisors are less well developed, or may be absent, in adult female, (Bello *et al.*, 2013). The canine teeth are conically shaped teeth (also called tusk or tushes) that develop in the space between the corners and the first premolar tooth in both upper and lower jaws. They are primarily fighting teeth and are usually larger in males than in females. Deciduous canines are later replaced by large, permanent canine teeth. The premolar teeth are the most forward of the grinding teeth set further back in the jaws and within the cheeks. Premolar teeth are all deciduous. While the molar teeth developed behind the premolar only as permanent teeth.

Post Mortem Meat Inspection

Post mortem examination was performed on each of the slaughtered camels, following the procedure as previously described by Corner (1994) and Asseged *et al.* (2004). Mandibular, retropharyngeal, bronchial, mediasternal, mesenteric and hepatic lymphnodes, were examined and organs including lungs, small intestine and kidneys were closely examined. No gross tuberculous lesions from slaughtered camels were seen.

Camel Tuberculosis Antibodies Test Procedure

Quiking® Bovine tuberculosis antibodies rapid test is a sandwich lateral flow immunochromatographic assay for the qualitative detection of bovine tuberculosis antibody in serum, procured from Quiking® Biotech Co. Limited Yanggao Road, Shanghai China.

The camel's whole blood sample was centrifuged at 30 rpm to collect serum. A reticle pipette 1 was used to

transfer 200µl of assay buffer in to a centrifugal tube. A reticle pipette 2 was used to transfer 20µl of serum into the centrifugal tube containing assay buffer and was thoroughly mixed with the pipette. The test kit cassette was removed from the foil pouch and was placed horizontally on a flat dry surface. Three drops of (about 100µl) of sample mixture was dropped into the cassette hole. The result was interpreted within 5 minutes after sample mixture was dropped into the cassette holes. Result after 6 minutes was considered invalid.

Interpretation of Result

The presence of both C and T band, no matter whether T band was clear or vague indicates positive test result. While the presence of only clear C band indicates negative test result.

Statistical Analysis

The results were presented in tables and charts. Chi square test (χ^2 - test) was used to analyze the significant relationship between the occurrences of *M. bovis* antibodies in serum of camels with regards to age and sex of the sampled animals.

RESULTS

The overall prevalence of tuberculosis in camels slaughtered at Sokoto Metropolitan abattoir during the study period was 30.8% based on screening for antibodies against *Mycobacterium bovis* using Rapid Bovine Tuberculosis Anti bodies test kit obtained from Quiking® Biotech Company Limited. No gross lesions of camel tuberculosis were seen at post mortem of the sampled animals. The number of female camels examined (62) was far lower than their male counterparts (188). Of these 27 of the females (43.6%) and 50 of the males (26.6%) were positive for *M. bovis* (Table 4.2). The highest examined camels were aged between 6 and 10 years. And of the 56 camels aged between 3 and 5 years 21 (37.5%) has the highest percentage of positive cases

Table 4.1: Age distribution of *M. bovis* antibodies in camels slaughtered at Sokoto Metropolitan abattoir (n= 250).

Age (Years)	Number of Animals in the Group	Number of Animals Positive	Percentage (%)
<2	17	4	23.5
3-5	56	21	37.5
6-10	114	35	30.7
>10	63	17	27.0
Total	250	77	30.8

$\chi^2=2.032$

P-Value =0.566

P> 0.05

Table 4.2: Sex distribution of *M. bovis* antibodies in camels slaughtered at Sokoto Metropolitan abattoir.

Sex	Number of Animals in Group	Number of Animals Positive	Percentage
Male	188	50	26.6
Female	62	27	43.5
Total	250	77	30.8

$\chi^2=5.517$

P-value =0.0188

P<0.05

Figure 4.1: Age distribution of *M. bovis* antibodies in camels slaughtered at Sokoto Metropolitan abattoir (n= 250).

Figure 4.2: Sex distribution of *M. bovis* antibodies in camels slaughtered at Sokoto Metropolitan abattoir.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Camel brought for slaughter at Sokoto Metropolitan abattoir had its source from mainly the state itself and its bordered neighbor Niger Republic. And on daily basis about 30 camels are slaughtered. In general information on camel tuberculosis is scanty. Few reports have been published on Camels tuberculosis in Nigeria and other countries. In the present abattoir-based study, the seroprevalence of tuberculosis in camels slaughtered at Sokoto Metropolitan abattoir was 30.8% using immunochromatographic assay technique. From the result 77 positive samples were observed out of 250 sampled camels.

The seroprevalence rate of camel tuberculosis in this present study using immunochromatographic assay technique specific for *M. bovis* was higher than (0.019%) reported by (Garba *et al.*, 2004) using post mortem lesion. This result, also indicate that post mortem examination of carcass is less sensitive in diagnosing camel tuberculosis, which is in agreement with the result of National Research Council (1994) that bovine tuberculosis is only seen in chronic stage. Also higher than 17% reported by (Kudi *et al.*, 2012) using rapid test in six in North Eastern Nigeria. The reasons for this might be due to the increase in proximity or contact between camel and cattle at the pastoralist area (Kinne *et al.*, 2006). Chi square statistical analysis was used to check for any association between the sex and age in relation to seroprevalence of camel tuberculosis in Sokoto Metropolitan abattoir. The result indicates that there was significant statistical association between the prevalence of camel tuberculosis and sex, while no statistical association occur between prevalence of camel tuberculosis and the age of the slaughtered animals. The absence of significant difference in regards to age of examined animals was in consistent with findings of (Mamo *et al.*, 2009) in the field. Though, the difference was not statistically significant. But higher Tb infection was observed in camels within the age group of 3 to 5 years (37.5%) followed by those between 6 to 10 years and those greater than 10 years with (30.7%) and (27.0%) respectively. Camels less than 2 years of age had the least prevalence of camel tuberculosis; this is in contrast with findings by (Kudi *et al.*, 2012) who reported higher prevalence among older animals (> 10 years). The high sensitivity and specificity of the kits to detect infection at any age could be the reason for higher prevalence among the middle group. And there is possibility that those camels with higher percentage of the infection (i.e. 3-5 years) could have acquired it from the abattoir, as less attention has been paid to them. Why more attention is been paid to the old ones as they were given tender care.

In this study, higher prevalence of the disease was recorded in female camels (43.5%) than the male (26.6%). This finding is in agreement with previous studies in

Ethiopia by Mamo *et al.* (2009) who reported a higher prevalence (6.25%) in female camels. This could be due to the fact that female camels were brought for slaughter at an older age after completion of their reproductive life (Inangolet *et al.*, 2008; Munyeme *et al.*, 2009) and this is directly related to long time exposure for Tb. Also Blood *et al.* (2007) has earlier reported higher prevalence of tuberculosis among female cattle than the male.

In conclusion, this study has shown the occurrence of tuberculosis in camels in the study area. It is very important to note that the incidence of camel tuberculosis is much higher than previously thought. And warrants further investigation to assess the distribution in camels of other pastoral area and its public health significance in the pastoral community where consumption of raw animal products is rampant.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is obvious that tuberculosis is a huge problem in Nigeria where there is a high incidence of the disease in camel, human, cattle, and other populations. A test and slaughter program for livestock is not really feasible and there is no attempt for vaccination of camels against tuberculosis. Therefore future research shall aim at the finding of an effective vaccine against camel tuberculosis. In order to control and prevent the occurrence of camel tuberculosis due to *M. bovis*, the Government should aim at providing vaccines as a reliable protection for both Animals and Humans. Also test- and- slaughter policy should be adopted as a backbone to national elimination programme

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